

Deliverable D.7.6 (part 1)

Report on the contribution to standardization

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Deliverable D.7.6 part 1 Report on the contribution to standardization

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Executive Summary

D7.6 part 1 is the first deliverable for subtask T7.2.2 “Contribution to the ongoing and future standardization developments” inside WP7 “Outreach, dissemination and communication”.

It presents the main conclusions of deliverable D7.5 “Report on the Standardization landscape and applicable standards” regarding the European and international standardisation landscape that is related to the Soil O-live project objectives and sets the strategy and actions that are being (or will be) carried out in order to disseminate the project towards possible future standardisation activities in the same field.

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE) is part of Soil O-live Consortium and, as a National Standardization Body (NSB), its main task in the project is to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the project (WP7. Outreach, dissemination and communications).

1. Introduction

The conclusions of deliverable D7.5 "Report on the standardisation landscape and applicable standards" shown that several European and international technical committees exist, as well as standards and standards under development, related to Soil O-live project. These technical committees and their standards may be helpful for the development of the different Soil O-live work packages.

These conclusions also introduced several actions that may be performed in collaboration with the identified standardisation technical committees, in order to interact with the standardisation system for disseminating the project findings, as well as to contribute to ongoing standards under development or future standards.

Considering the above-mentioned information, this document specifies a strategy and an action plan that links the most relevant identified standardisation technical committees and the possible collaboration activities, also specifying possible dates, responsibilities and what is needed from Soil O-live partners.

2. Strategy

The contribution to standardization of Soil O-live is based in the interaction with the relevant Standardization Technical Committees and in the initiation of a standardization process. The strategy comprises the actions represented in the following diagram and explaining below:

2.1. First contact with the standardization technical committees

The objective of these first contacts is to raise awareness about Soil O-live among the relevant standardization committees and to ease subsequent contacts.

Different categories of stakeholders at European/international level are present in these committees, so the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback is asked to gather any view, opinion or advice about the project and the standardization possibilities or needs. Additionally, these first contacts are useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardization process, moreover this first step eases future contacts if this process is launched within a standardization committee.

2.2. Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the relevant CEN and/or ISO technical committees.

Two factors determine the more suitable interactions: the impact/relevance of the standardization works of the standardization committees and the feasibility of initiating a standardization process within a standardization committee (versus initiating the standardization process within a standardization workshop, details

are given below). The ways of interaction of the project with the standardization committees include:

1. Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardization committees. This allows to detect the initiation of standardization works that can be relevant for Soil O-live and the progress of significant existing under-development standards. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardization activity resulting in updates of D7.5.
2. Further contact with the standardization committees to update the progress of Soil O-live. This is achievable by delivering reports, by attending relevant technical committees' meetings or by joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardization process, on the other hand this further contact is mandatory towards the standardization committees directly covering (if it where the case) the subject promoted by Soil O-live to undergo a standardization process.
3. The participation of one or more Soil O-live partners in the standardization technical committees. Standardization is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardization Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardization committee and is valuable if the standardization process is going to be initiated within the standardization committee. Some of the partners are already participating in some of the identified standardization committees.
4. The establishment of a formal liaison of Soil O-live with the standardization committees. It is recommended only when the work of the standardization committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected. The figure of project liaison is recognized in CEN but it is not very effective in ISO.

2.3. Standardization process

The main objective of the standardization activities in Soil O-live is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners the feasible results to go through a standardization process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardization shall be considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and IPR) and the standardization context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardization committees):

1. Development of a new standard within a standardization workshop. A standardization workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardization committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures faster and more flexible. A standardization workshop is created when there is a need of developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardization committees or when these committees are not interested in developing such standard (e.g. it does not fit in their work programme). If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardization committee it shall be informed and allow for the launching of the standardization workshop.
2. Considering that the standardization workshop option is interesting for Soil O-live mainly in the European environment, the standardization workshop will be named hereinafter as CEN Workshop. The standard produced by a CEN Workshop is called CEN Workshop Agreement, typically named as CWA. The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for the framework of the R&I projects.
3. Standardization within a standardization committee. It may be interesting or needed that the results of Soil O-live to go through the standardization process are standardized within a standardization committee. The possible scenarios are:
 - Development of a new standard within a standardization committee. When there is a result of Soil O-live to be promoted to a standard in a field covered by a standardization committee and such committee decides to include this development in its work programme. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardization committee but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardization committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.
 - Contribute to an on-going standard. As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardization landscape it may be found that the results of Soil O-live are covered by an on-going standard but that these results do not fit in the current draft of the standard. Gaps in standards may be found in both, standards that are being developed from a new initiative and standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.
 - Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review. The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardization committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardization committee.

- Outline of a future standard. Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardization (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

3. Action plan

3.1. Standardization technical committees

Deliverable D7.5 gave a landscape of European (CEN) and international (ISO) technical committees developing standards. Nevertheless, for the next steps in Subtask 7.2.2 it may be advisable to consider to:

- Differentiate between technical committees for dissemination and technical committees for dissemination and cooperation, since the Soil O-live objectives and findings may be subject of different levels of interest among technical committees.
- Differentiate between technical committees producing standards and technical committees adopting standards, since part of CEN testing standards are adoption of ISO standards, which means that the CEN standards are the same as the original ISO standards, and for Soil O-live objectives the technical committees producing standards are more relevant.

With these considerations, Table 1 shows the different standardisation technical committees included in D7.5 and the expected degree of interaction with them.

Table 1. Expected degree of interaction with standardisation technical committees

Standardization area	Standardization Technical Committee	Expected degree of interaction		
		Dissemination	Dissemination and cooperation	No interaction
Soil quality	CEN/TC 444 "Test methods for environmental characterization of solid matrices"		✓	
	ISO/TC 190 "Soil quality"		✓	
	ISO/TC 190/SC 3 "Chemical and physical characterization"		✓	
	ISO/TC 190/SC 4 "Biological characterization"		✓	
	ISO/TC 190/SC 7 "Impact assessment"		✓	
Microplastics	CEN/TC 249 "Plastics"			✓
	ISO /TC 61/SC 14 "Plastics. Environmental aspects"			✓
Oil quality	CEN/TC 307 "Oilseeds, vegetable and animal fats and oils and their by-products - Methods of sampling and analysis"	✓		
	ISO/TC 34/SC 11 "Animal and vegetable fats and oils"	✓		
Geographic information	ISO/TC 211 "Geographic information/Geomatics"			✓

Environmental management	ISO/TC 207 "Environmental management"			✓
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Those committees related with areas where no relevant innovation of interest for the committees would be expected during the project, no interaction have been proposed.

A close relationship with the "dissemination and cooperation" technical committees should be established for a continuous bidirectional information since some Soil O-live results could be expected to be standardised or included in standardisation deliverables.

For the dissemination and cooperation activities with each technical committee, the contact addressed to the Secretaries and Chairpersons of each committee have been identified. For data privacy reasons these have not been included in this document.

A text for the communication will include:

- Brief introduction of the project;
- Explanation of the aim of the standardization activities in the project.
Presentation of UNE as part of the standardization community and as the project partner leading these activities;
- Showing the link of the work developed in Soil O-live with the relevant standardization committee highlighting specific project objectives and relevant standards ;
- Link to the Soil O-live webpage.

See Annex A for an example of the general text. It will be modified depending on the technical committee reached out.

Also, a power point presentation with a brief description of Soil O-live, its objectives and Work Packages of interest, will be attached in the communication. See Annex B.

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Presentation of UNE as part of the standardization community and as the project partner leading these activities;
- Showing the link of the work developed in Soil O-Live with the relevant standardization committee highlighting specific project objectives and relevant standards ;
- Link to the Soil O-Live webpage.

See Annex B for the general text. In addition, a summary document prepared by UNE and UJA was included in the communication summarizing the most important data of the project and the results achieved so far (see Annex C).

NOTE: by the time this deliverable is being published (June 2024) CEN/TC 444 and ISO/TC 190 secretary and Chairmans have recently been contacted and they have expressed their interest in further information about the objectives and activities of Soil O-live.

In the following deliverables for Subtask T 7.2.2 the actions derived from this contact and from the future contact to Oil Quality committees will be described

3.2. Further actions to be carried out

With all the previously presented information, the action plan including actions, responsibilities and dates can be done drafted, in order to help the contribution to standardisation of Soil O-live and deliverables D7.6 part 2 and 3, which are expected to be finished on M36 and M60.

Table 2. Next actions

#	Action	Related TC	Responsible	Date
A1	Follow up of TCs standardisation activities	All identified TCs with interaction defined in Table 1	UNE	Continuous (M18 to M60)
A2	Presentation of the project in TCs meetings	“Dissemination and cooperation” TCs of table 1	All relevant partners	When needed
B1	Participation in a TC	“Dissemination and cooperation” TCs of table 1	All relevant partners / consortium	If defined, continuous
C1	Identification and elaboration of standardisation proposals	“Dissemination and cooperation” TCs of table 1	All partners	Continuous (M18 to M60)
C2	Development of standardisation deliverables	n.a.	All partners	Continuous (M18 to M60)

This action plan will be continuously adapted to the project needs and partners' feedback, as well as completed with available information. At this moment it is not possible to define each action timing more accurately, but it establishes the next steps regarding the contribution to standardisation.

4. Use of already existing standards

The aim of D7.5 was to provide information on the current status of standardization, both at International and European level, for the Soil O-live Project Scope. In this manner, the information contained in the deliverable could be consulted by the other Soil O-live WP experts, in order to identify and use the applicable standard requirements, methodologies, processes, terminology, etc. which can contribute to the project, avoiding duplication of efforts, ensuring adaptation to market conditions and maximizing interoperability and compatibility with existing ones.

As a result, several standards or standards in development were identified as useful for the project and were shared with the correspondent WP leaders in order to study the potential use of the standard. They are listed in Table 3

Table 3. Standards used in the WPs

Reference	Title
ISO/AWI 18721	Assessment of ecological soil functions: indicators and methods
ISO 11260:2018	Soil quality. Determination of effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation level using barium chloride solution
ISO 10694:1995	Soil quality. Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion (elementary analysis)
ISO/TS 14256-1:2003	Soil quality. Determination of nitrate, nitrite and ammonium in field-moist soils by extraction with potassium chloride solution. Part 1: Manual method
ISO 14238:2012	Soil quality. Biological methods. Determination of nitrogen mineralization and nitrification in soils and the influence of chemicals on these processes
ISO 15685:2012	Soil quality. Determination of potential nitrification and inhibition of nitrification. Rapid test by ammonium oxidation
ISO 17155:2012	Soil quality- Determination of abundance and activity of soil microflora using respiration curve
ISO 11269-2:2012	Soil quality. Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora. Part 2: Effects of contaminated soil on the emergence and early growth of higher plants
ISO 16072:2002	Soil quality. Laboratory methods for determination of microbial soil respiration
ISO 23265:2022	Soil quality. Test for estimating organic matter decomposition in contaminated soil
ISO 11269-1:2012	Soil quality. Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora .Part 1: Method for the measurement of inhibition of root growth
ISO 22030:2005	Soil quality. Biological methods. Chronic toxicity in higher plants
ISO 23400:2021	Guidelines for the determination of organic carbon and nitrogen stocks and their variations in mineral soils at field scale
ISO 9936:2016	Animal and vegetable fats and oils. Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents by high-performance liquid chromatography.
ISO 5555:2001	Animal and vegetable fats and oils. Sampling.
ISO 20691:2022	Biotechnology. Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences
ISO 20397-2:2021	Biotechnology. Massively parallel sequencing. Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data
ISO/CD 20397-3	Biotechnology. Massively parallel sequencing. Part 3: General requirements and guidance for metagenomics

ISO/TS 24420:2023	Biotechnology. Massively parallel DNA sequencing. General requirements for data processing of shotgun metagenomic sequences
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5. Conclusions

As a result of D7.5 several actions have been scheduled and will be implemented in the following months as part of the strategy of dissemination of Soil O-live and as an opportunity for stablish synergies with the European and International standardization organizations.

The use of already existing standards in Soil O-live activities has proved the adaptation to market conditions and the opportunities to maximize the interoperability and compatibility with existing ones.

ANNEX A. Communication text

Subject CEN-ISO/TC XXX. SOIL O-LIVE HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT

Dear Ms/Mr. XXX and Ms/Mr. XXX,

I'm Rosa Cepas, project manager for the agrifood sector at UNE (Spanish Association for Standardization).

I'm addressing you on behalf of the Horizon Europe project [Soil O-live](#) which aim is *to address various of the challenges faced by the olive growers in the Mediterranean region (such as intensive agriculture practices, land degradation, biodiversity loss and functionality reduction) through various multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary projects.*

This project is assessing the environmental condition of olive grove soils on a large scale in the major Mediterranean olive production areas and is examining how pollution and land degradation affect olive groves' soils, investigating the connection between soil health and the quality and safety of olive oil, and will implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices, and establish strict ecological thresholds for healthy European olive groves.

As part of this project, under the responsibility of UNE (Spanish standardization body) representing CEN/CENELEC in Soil O-live, specific standardization activities are included to:

- Ensure compatibility with existing methodologies by the identification of relevant existing standards,
- Maximize dissemination to proper stakeholders by addressing the relevant standardization technical committees and
- Contribute with the findings and knowledge generated during the project to the development of standardization in the field.

We have identified CEN/ISO/TC XXX as a closely related TC to the Soil O-live scope, and indeed some of the standards of these TC were identified as very relevant for the project, including general standards for XXXX.

The objective of this contact is twofold: firstly, to raise awareness of the project to this TC and gather feedback on any suggestions, questions or comments; and secondly, to inform you of Soil O-live's intention to contribute to standardization from the selected/standardizable project results in future steps of the project.

(CEN/TC'S ONLY) The contribution to standardization may be orientated towards generating new pre-standards (CEN Workshop Agreements) or participating at TC level. The decision will be based on a number of factors,

including the nature of the results in question and the standardization landscape at the relevant time.

(ISO/TC'S ONLY) The contribution to standardization may be orientated towards participating at TC level.

Please find attached a brief summary containing the most relevant information about Soil O-live.

Further detailed information is available on the webpage <https://soilolive.eu/>.

Please feel free to circulate this information to your TC members or to anyone you consider potentially interested in the objectives and results of the project.

With the project now nearly 2/5 progressed, we would be very grateful if you could provide us with feedback regarding the interest of this project for the activity of the TC.

Additionally, any suggestions, questions or comments related to the project would be very useful.

If you find that additional information would be welcome, as well as other kind of contact (a dedicated telco, attending to a TC, SC or WG meeting to explain the project, etc.) we would be pleased to address it.

Thank you in advance for your attention and looking forward for your reply.

Best regards

Rosa Cepas Aguayo

Agri-food service

ANNEX B. Dissemination Leaflet

Spain</p>	Start date	End date	1 January 2023	31 December 2027		
Start date	End date					
1 January 2023	31 December 2027					
<p>Call: HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-02-03 — Linking soil health to nutritional and safe food</p>						

SOIL O-LIVE CONSORTIUM

World production below average in 2023/24...

Source: International Olive Council, Member States declarations. Note: excl. pomace oil.

WORLD	-2%
EU	8%
non-EU	-14%

WORLD	-19%
EU	-24%
non-EU	-11%

... and EU production remains below average.

Source: International Olive Council, Member States declarations. Note: excl. pomace oil.

EU production in 2023/24 expected 24% below 5-year average

EVOO prices back to record-high levels

To achieve such production, approximately six million hectares, mainly in the EU Mediterranean countries, are dedicated to cultivating olive trees, encompassing organic, traditional, and high-density intensive groves

Soil erosion by water (tonnes per ha per year), 2010, EU-28, NUTS 3 (left) and Severe soil erosion in agricultural lands (right) - % of agricultural land with > 11t/annually.
Source: Joint Research Centre, European Commission

- Poor land management is extensive across the cultivation area.
- Absence of plant cover along the whole year
- There is a massive use of phytochemicals used since late 70's for pest control and productivity

DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL

on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law)

Proportion of land affected by soil degradation in the EU

60-70 % of EU soils are unhealthy

GENERAL GOAL

To perform the **FIRST RIGOROUS DIAGNOSTIC OF THE WHOLE ENVIRONMENTAL SITUATION OF OLIVE ORCHARDS SOILS** at a broad scale, comprising the **MOST IMPORTANT AREAS AND AGRONOMIC MODES OF OLIVE PRODUCTION** across the Mediterranean region and **ITS RELATIONSHIPS TO OLIVE OIL QUALITY** across the food chain

PARTICULAR GOALS

GOAL 1

To analyze the impact of pollution and land degradation on soils from olive groves in terms of multi-biodiversity and ecological function at different levels of organization and scales.

GOAL 2

To investigate the relationship of soil health status with the quality and safety of olive oil.

GOAL 3

To implement effective soil amendments and cutting-edge ecological restoration practices that promote manifest soil biodiversity and functionality enhancements that should be eventually translated to improvements in olive oil quality and safety.

GOAL 4

To define rigorous ecological thresholds that allow implementing future explicit norms and regulations to design a novel future certification for healthy soils in European olive oil.

ORCHARDS STUDIED in Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Spain
ORCHADS TYPE: traditional, intensive and organic

WORK PACKAGES

- **WORK PACKAGE 1**
Coordination and management
- **WORK PACKAGE 2**
Soil Pollution in Mediterranean olive groves
- **WORK PACKAGE 3**
Soil erosion and land degradation
- **WORK PACKAGE 4**
Microbiome of olive groves
- **WORK PACKAGE 5**
Soil Biodiversity
- **WORK PACKAGE 6**
Ecosystem services
- **WORK PACKAGE 7**
Outreach, dissemination and communications

WORK PACKAGE 2

SOIL POLLUTION IN MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES

1. Analyze pre and post operational presence of herbicides, pesticides, fungicide and copper residues in olive groves.
2. Carry out a life cycle assessment (LCA) to assess the environmental situation of the decontamination treatment applied to Soil O-live, evaluating among other impact categories, the carbon and water footprint, freshwater ecotoxicity, agricultural land occupation and human toxicity.
3. Pre-screening of chemical and electrochemical restoration strategies;
4. Design and construction of a portable system for the onsite electrochemical generation of green oxidants and the evaluation of the best treatment strategies in pilot olive groves selected for elevated soil pollution by pesticides;
5. Investigate the extent of microplastic presence in olive grove soils and their impact on soil functionality
6. Evaluation of the presence of antibiotics and other veterinarian residues
7. Identify Antibiotic Resistance Genes (ARG) in the soil microbiome;
8. Assess pre-operational and post-operational levels of nitrification and carbon stock accumulated in soils from olive groves with different land management.

WORK PACKAGE 3

SOIL EROSION AND LAND DEGRADATION

1. Design and develop a harmonized framework to assess and monitor the state of soil degradation due to erosion under cultivation of olive trees in line with the objectives of the European Soil Mission. This framework will span from remote mapping and modelling land use effects on soil health as well as calibration and validation with selected tracers of sediment transport and indicators of soil degradation
2. Test and implement the new methodological framework in a set of selected pilot testing sites of the Soil O-live project under different climatic and land management conditions.
3. Develop and deploy a pan-mediterranean modelling-based assessment coupled to remote mapping and ground-based observations validation, to spatial-temporally define the European olive groves exposed to degradation processes.
4. Extrapolate the modelling into the future and develop a machine-learning approach to forecast future soil and land degradation scenarios under land use and climate change.

WORK PACKAGE 4
MICROBIOME OF OLIVE GROVES

1. Analyze the microbial communities of the olive rhizosphere, olive roots and bulk soil;
2. Understand the impact of land management and pollution on the symbiotic interaction between mycorrhizae in olive trees and consequences for tree health and groundcovers;
3. Conduct advances practices of microbe restoration in selected olive groves
4. Analyze functionality of diversity of bacteria and fungi communities and services, such as soil structure, litter decomposition, organic carbon storage and nutrients cycling in selected restored olive groves.

WORK PACKAGE 5
SOIL BIODIVERSITY

1. Design and develop a harmonized framework to assess and monitor the state of soil degradation due to erosion under cultivation of olive trees in line with the objectives of the European Soil Mission. This WP will investigate the pre-operational and post-operational abundance and biodiversity (taxonomic, genetic and functional) of key soil organisms as: free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes, ants, seed bank composition and groundcovers.
 - In those olive groves which seed bank is nil and plant cover absent we will restore plant diversity by seeding and plant growing either in middle rows of the olive tree lines and in rills, and it will investigate functionality enhancements of nematode, ants, seed bank composition and vegetation groundcovers in restored olive groves. In addition, we will analyze the genetic diversity within species in key groups plants to evaluate impact of land management and soil pesticide residues on nucleotide diversity.
 - An estimation of impact of land management on genetic variation on ecologically important traits on selected species of the natural groundcover is also planned.
 - We will determine ploidy levels of plants growing in olive orchards, aiming to unravel ploidy levels of the groundcovers in olive groves with different agronomic management in order to investigate the impact of pesticides on whole genome duplication events in plants.
2. Test and implement the new methodological framework in a set of selected pilot testing sites of the Soil O-live project under different climatic and land management conditions.

WORK PACKAGE 6

ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

1. To estimate ecosystem fluxes (CO₂ fixation and H₂O evotranspiration) above and below tree canopy in olive groves with different management
2. To survey the abundance and incidence of two olive tree pests, olive moth and olive fly in olive groves differing in management across the region
3. To develop a digital twin corresponding to three types of olive groves in order to support the integration of multi-source soil and ecosystem data.
4. To screen the physiology status of the olive trees at each agronomic situation during olive oil production in fruits (September). For that, we Will measure pre-operational and post-operational isotopic signatures ¹²C/¹³C for water use efficiency and estimation of C/N ratio and phosphorus.
5. Evaluate the presence of pesticide residues in olive oil from olive groves subjected to restoration measurements.
6. Evaluate the olive oil quality from the different management scenarios and study the impact of restoration on the overall quality of the product.

WORK PACKAGE 7

OUTREACH, DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATIONS

1. To ensure that geospatial data created during the diagnostic and effectiveness stages are open, well-documented, interoperable, and geo-linkable;
2. To create technical guidelines and tools for data interoperability assurance and replicability;
3. To provide initial information for other WPs to ensure compatibility and interoperability with existing market standards;
4. To use the standardization system to disseminate project results;
5. To contribute to the development of new standards that facilitate market acceptance of the project results;
6. To communicate the main project activities and results to increase the number of farmers who carry out sustainability and quality practices in their olive groves;
7. To analyze farmer behavior towards sustainable agronomic practices that improve soil health in olive grove cultivation, in order to determine the origin of farmer resistance to change;
8. To analyze gender roles in land management, soil health, and olive quality;
9. To propose effective policies for future promotion of a change in growing mode in olive groves

